

KEY FACTORS INFLUENCING THE INCLUSION OF THE METRO IN MULTIMODAL FREIGHT TRANSPORT

1. INTRODUCTION

For several decades now, the population in many parts of the world has tended to move to large cities, making them increasingly larger and more demanding of products and services. New technologies and consumer habits have encouraged the use of e-commerce, with all that it involves in terms of logistics and its consequences (CO₂ emissions, waste, traffic congestion, etc.).

The 2030 Agenda promoted by the UN sets out a series of challenges known as 'Sustainable Development Goals', some of which are aimed at promoting actions to improve the health and sustainability of the planet and its ecosystems, reducing waste generated and the impact on the environment. These objectives have been agreed by 193 countries that have committed to promoting them through their institutions, which will undoubtedly generate competitive advantages for the companies that better adapt. Therefore, logistics and e-commerce must adapt and innovate to align themselves with these objectives, not only for reasons of responsibility, but also for reasons of profitability and survival.

Aligned to this, the use of sustainable means of transport such as the metro network is an innovative option for the transport of goods to and from the center of large cities, thus avoiding the surface circulation of much more polluting vehicles. It is a fact that the main purpose of a metro network is mass passenger transport, but the capacities of these networks are sized for peak periods (rush hour), while during the rest of the day the facilities and trains are underused. It is at these times that extra capacity (trains, drivers, facilities, etc.) can be used for freight transport without affecting passenger services.

The possibilities are enormous and there are a multitude of scenarios that could be evaluated, tested and validated, but the European FOR-FREIGHT project has proposed a specific business case that stands out for its high level of innovation:

The case put forward consists of linking and sharing information between the different freight transport agents involved in the chain, since a cargo ship from the shipping company COSCO arrives at the port of Valencia until the order asked by a consumer is picked up at a locker located in a Metro de Madrid station, passing first through a DHL intermediate warehouse. In addition, the FOR-FREIGHT platform provides assistance to the different agents to take the most appropriate decisions based on lockers occupancy, vehicles available for transport, minimization of greenhouse gas emissions, estimated work capacity, etc.

Focusing on the part that affects the Metro de Madrid network, the process would be as follows:

DHL Goods Delivery via Metro Train

- A DHL truck delivers the previously sorted goods to a Metro depot, a place where the trains are maintained and which is generally on the outskirts of the city.

- The goods are loaded onto a train that will not take passengers on its journey. The inclusion of this train will not affect the passenger service normally offered by Metro de Madrid.

- For the transport of goods in the train, cages or containers designed for this purpose will be used, so that they adapt perfectly to the facilities and the trains.

- At each station where a locker has been set up, the train will stop and the goods going to that locker will be unloaded.

- There, a DHL operator will put the orders in the locker and thus the customer will be able to pick it up with a code that he/she will have received beforehand.

Therefore, there is no need for any trucks or vans to enter the city center and drive for hours to deliver goods in the whole process, which undoubtedly reduces surface traffic and greenhouse gas emissions. This is the biggest advantage of using the metro network for freight transport. But it is also very important to be able to take advantage of the capillarity of the network and the large number of stations where lockers could be installed, which would allow a large part of the population of the Community of Madrid to have one of these delivery points very close to their homes.

2. KEY FACTORS

The benefits of utilizing metro networks for freight transport are evident, and societal trends alongside evolving consumer habits are driving the adoption of such innovative logistics solutions. However, the question remains: is it feasible to leverage the metro network and its surplus capacity for this purpose?

To address this, several key considerations must be evaluated when integrating the metro into the logistics chain:

- **Timetable Adaptation:** Freight operations must be scheduled during off-peak hours to avoid disruptions to passenger services, ensuring optimal utilization of surplus capacity.

- **Minimal Impact on Passengers:** The integration of freight transport should have a negligible effect on passenger experience, including train schedules, station accessibility, and overall service reliability.
- **Safety Assurance:** Safety must be maintained at all times for personnel, transported goods, trains, and facilities. Comprehensive safety protocols are critical to the success of such operations.
- **Streamlined Loading and Unloading Operations:** These processes must be rapid and standardized to align with the constraints of passenger transport schedules. Efficient handling minimizes dwell times and ensures smooth operations across the network.

By adhering to these principles, the last-mile freight transport solution proposed in the **FOR-FREIGHT project** represents a groundbreaking innovation. Notably, this approach to freight transport is not currently implemented in any metro system globally. The core concept is to utilize the existing network's capacity without requiring significant modifications or redesigns, making it both cost-effective and operationally efficient.

Key Factors for Metro Operators Considering Urban Freight Distribution

For any metro operator contemplating urban freight distribution, several critical factors must be addressed to ensure the viability and success of such projects. These factors are outlined below:

A. Operational Feasibility

1. **Dedicated vs. Shared Trains:** This is the first question that must be resolved. In large cities, it is extremely challenging to combine passenger and freight transport due to the lack of surplus capacity, as all resources are typically allocated to passenger transport.
2. **Timetables:** Freight operations must align with non-peak hours to avoid disruptions to passenger services. A thorough analysis of train schedules is essential to identify windows of surplus capacity.
3. **Impact on Passengers:** Freight activities must have minimal impact on the passenger experience, including station accessibility, train frequency, and overall service reliability.

B. Infrastructure and Key Elements

1. **Train Type:** The train type in each metro system directly affects freight capacity. The layout of seats, grab bars, and other elements must be carefully analyzed to evaluate their impact on the ability to transport goods.
2. **Stations with Elevators:** Elevators are essential for moving goods between underground platforms and the surface. Operations are inefficient without vertical lifting equipment.
3. **Platforms:** Platform size significantly influences the ease of loading and unloading operations. Large platforms enable simpler and more efficient operations, while small or narrow platforms present logistical challenges.

4. **Microhubs:** Microhubs are necessary for last-mile home deliveries. This operational model requires small warehouses for the final delivery to customers using complementary methods such as cargo bikes, foot couriers, etc.
5. **Parcel Transport Equipment:** Roller cages or baskets for transporting goods must be designed to account for the physical characteristics of metro trains and stations (elevators, access doors, height, etc.) and safety regulations that may apply. Once these requirements are met, the equipment must also maximize loading capacity.

C. Safety Considerations

1. **Personnel and Goods Safety:** The safety of operational staff and goods must be ensured through rigorous protocols to prevent accidents and protect the integrity of the freight.
2. **Infrastructure Adaptations:** Measures should be implemented to secure cargo during train movements and prevent damage to passenger train interiors, such as seats and grab bars.
3. **Operational Security:** Protocols must be in place to prevent theft or tampering with goods during transit and handling.

D. Speed and Efficiency

1. **Rapid Loading and Unloading:** Processes must be highly efficient to minimize train dwell times at stations. Delays could disrupt service schedules and reduce overall system efficiency.
2. **Streamlined Logistics:** Handling equipment, such as roller cages and specialized containers, must be optimized for metro platforms and train dimensions to ensure swift and seamless operations.
3. **End-to-End Synchronization:** Coordination with logistics operators is crucial to reduce waiting times, improve throughput, and maintain overall supply chain efficiency.

E. Environmental and Urban Impact

1. **Reduction of Surface Vehicles:** A key objective is to minimize the presence of delivery trucks and vans in urban centers, thereby reducing traffic congestion and emissions.
2. **Integration with Existing Infrastructure:** Locker placement should maximize accessibility for end users while maintaining smooth passenger flow through stations.
3. **Emissions Tracking:** Implementing tools to measure and report CO2 emission reductions is critical for demonstrating the environmental benefits of the project and strengthening stakeholder support.

F. Collaboration Among Stakeholders

An innovative model like urban freight distribution through metro networks requires collaboration among key stakeholders, including transport operators, manufacturers, and

logistics service providers. The goal is to improve individual and collective economies of scale and scope in terms of supply chain efficiency (total logistics cost across the value chain), productivity, and overall system effectiveness. These improvements must be achieved without compromising the competitive advantages of the stakeholders involved.

In this sense, it is essential to consider the communication and management tools that any of the stakeholders may have already in use. Different stakeholders must be able to smoothly integrate their legacy systems into the common FOR-FREIGHT platform so critical information is effectively shared. Core information to be shared refers, among others, to: request and acceptance/denial of orders between logistics provider and lockers operator (Metro in FOR-FREIGHT project), updated intake capacity of the lockers at each of the stations, delivery capacity of the logistics provider, planned quantity of parcels to be delivered in each station, etc.

Allowing the tracking of the freight at different key locations of the entire process is also critical to ensure collaboration among stakeholders. As in FOR-FREIGHT project occurs, both logistics operator and Metro have real-time access to the time stamps through QR code scanning of the sealed roller cages containing the parcels to be delivered. This ensures that the freight is secured, and losses are minimized. In case any inconvenient may come up during the transportation process, the location and time frames where it occurred will be easily identified. This capacity will directly and positively affect the retailers interest in choosing the innovative business model of logistics operator-Metro in addition to the sustainability and cost-effectiveness reasons.

3. REPLICATION POTENTIAL

Taking all of these aspects into account, the case put forward in the FOR-FREIGHT project is a very interesting proposal that can be replicated in other suburbans around the world. Specifically, FOR-FREIGHT proposes the following innovations:

- Use of lockers throughout the metro network: Due to the distribution of stations throughout the city, a place accessible to a large part of the population could be available just a few minutes from their homes. Almost every suburban in the world has a similar situation, so this innovation could be easily adapted.

To install these lockers, a series of recommendations should be followed:

- i. Designate stations with a sufficient volume of passengers and/or potential customers in nearby areas.
- ii. Place the lockers preferably in the area before ticket validation, to facilitate access for all potential customers.
- iii. Identify locations that require minimal movement by the staff responsible for restocking the lockers, in order to avoid interference with passengers.

- Freight transport with trains: In order to be able to undertake this task, the metro network must have surplus capacity, which is the case for all suburbans in the world. However, this surplus must be produced at times that are compatible with the needs of logistics operators and

end customers, so the feasibility of its implementation would need to be analysed on a case-by-case basis.

- Use of a single platform for information exchange and decision-making: The FOR-FREIGHT platform provides the companies involved in the process with certain indicators for decision-making, as well as mechanisms for communicating needs and validating them. This platform would make it easier for several transport companies to use the service, but in general, each company uses its own applications. How difficult or easy it is for companies to adapt to the platform proposed by FOR-FREIGHT will be key to the success of the project. The platform has been developed in a simple and adaptable way, so it is expected that companies will not encounter many difficulties on its implementation.

- Use of load tracking devices. This aspect is already widely used in the sector, so its use should not be a problem. The only difficulty may arise in locating goods inside metro tunnels in operations that do not have WiFi coverage throughout their network.

- Integration with Green Logistics. The replication of the FOR-FREIGHT model presents an opportunity to promote environmentally friendly practices by incorporating green logistics solutions, such as the use of electric vehicles for first-mile and last-mile connections. This would further enhance the sustainability benefits of the system.

- Collaboration with Local Authorities. The successful implementation of freight transport via metro networks relies on close cooperation with municipal governments and urban planners. Local authorities can provide regulatory support, facilitate integration with existing logistics systems, and encourage the adoption of sustainable practices through subsidies or incentives.

- Adaptability to Local Urban Characteristics. Every city possesses distinct characteristics, such as population density, station layout, and existing transport infrastructure. To effectively implement the FOR-FREIGHT model, it is essential to conduct a detailed analysis of these factors and tailor the approach accordingly. In cities with densely populated urban centers, the deployment of lockers could be supplemented with additional micro-distribution solutions, such as drone deliveries or autonomous vehicles, to enhance last-mile delivery efficiency.

- Regulatory framework. Although there is no specific regulation for the use of metro trains for freight transport, any such operation must comply with:

i. Railway safety standards:

- Compliance Requirements: Operations must adhere to EU Directive 2016/797 on railway safety, transposed into Spanish law via Real Decreto 412/2014. This mandates strict protocols for handling goods, including secure stowage of parcels in trains to prevent movement during transit, fire prevention measures (e.g., non-flammable containers), and emergency response plans tailored to mixed passenger-freight scenarios. Lockers installed in stations must comply with UNE-EN 50131 for electronic security systems, ensuring protection against tampering or unauthorized access.

- Risks: Failure to meet these standards could result in accidents (e.g., loose parcels causing derailment risks) or safety breaches, leading to investigations by the Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Ferroviaria (AESF) and potential sanctions under Law 38/2015 on the railway sector. Passenger safety must remain uncompromised, requiring segregation of freight operations (e.g., dedicated trains or compartments).
 - Mitigation: Conduct safety audits certified by the AESF, implement training for staff on freight handling, and install CCTV-monitored lockers with biometric or QR-code access to enhance security.
- ii. Interoperability conditions, especially if the metro network connects with other rail systems.
- Compliance Requirements: If the metro network interfaces with other rail systems (e.g., Cercanías in Madrid), the operation must align with EU Directive 2012/34 establishing a single European railway area. This includes standardizing freight containers to meet Technical Specifications for Interoperability (TSI), ensuring compatibility with existing rail infrastructure, and integrating tracking software compliant with ETCS (European Train Control System) standards for real-time monitoring.
 - Risks: Non-standardized equipment or software could disrupt rail operations, particularly if freight trains share tracks with regional services. Lack of interoperability may also limit partnerships with logistics operators like DHL or Amazon.
 - Mitigation: Develop standardized freight containers (e.g., roller cages) certified for rail use, and adopt interoperable tracking systems (e.g., API-integrated platforms) to ensure seamless coordination with external rail networks.
- iii. Local urban transport regulations.
- Compliance Requirements: The project must integrate with Madrid's Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (PMUS) and Low Emission Zones (ZBE), as mandated by the Municipal Ordinance on Air Quality and Sustainability (2021). Installing lockers in stations requires permits under the General Urban Planning Plan (PGOU), ensuring compliance with accessibility standards (Law 51/2003) and urban design regulations. The operation must also demonstrate environmental benefits, such as reduced CO2 emissions, to align with the Spanish Climate Change and Energy Transition Law 7/2021.
 - Risks: Unauthorized modifications to station infrastructure (e.g., locker installations) could lead to fines from the Ayuntamiento de Madrid. Failure to align with ZBE goals may jeopardize funding opportunities, such as NextGenerationEU grants.

- Mitigation: Secure urban planning permits through consultations with the Local Administration, and quantify environmental impacts (e.g., 500-1,000 tons of CO2 saved annually, based on Metro de Madrid’s 2024 pilot data) to justify compliance with sustainability mandates.

Summary table:

Regulatory Category	Key Compliance Points	Main Risks / Mitigation
Railway Safety Standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Directive 2016/797 / RD 412/2014. • Secure stowage, fire prevention, emergency protocols. • Lockers per UNE-EN 50131. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risks: Accident, AESF sanctions. • Mitigation: AESF audits, staff training, CCTV & biometric lockers.
Interoperability Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Directive 2012/34 (Single European Railway Area). • Freight containers per TSI. • ETCS-compliant tracking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risks: Disruption, non-compatibility with DHL/Amazon. • Mitigation: Standard containers, interoperable APIs.
Local Urban Transport Regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PMUS, ZBE & PGOU compliance. • Accessibility (Law 51/2003). • Law 7/2021 (Climate Change). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risks: Fines, loss of funding. • Mitigation: Permits from Ayuntamiento, prove CO₂ savings (500–1,000 t/yr).

Moreover, since the activity carried out by metro companies is limited to passenger transport, in order to engage in freight transport, it is necessary to change the company’s corporate purpose and assess whether this new activity requires any additional changes in terms of accounting and taxation.

In the FOR-FREIGHT project, lockers are designated as the final destination for goods. However, in cases where goods are widely dispersed or delivery volumes are high, it may be necessary to evaluate the feasibility of establishing warehouses or microhubs. These facilities could act as temporary intermediate points, enabling efficient sorting and final distribution to lockers through complementary methods such as cargo bikes or pedestrian couriers.

With all of the above, it can be concluded that the case proposed in the FOR-FREIGHT project can serve as a model for many suburbs in the world, as long as the conditions mentioned above are met.

For the cities that can opt for this alternative in the last mile delivery of e-commerce goods, the advantages and benefits obtained are those described above but can be summarised as a reduction in environmental impact, a reduction in the number of vehicles on the surface and providing the end customer with a network of collection points for their orders.

Moreover, assuming the use of a single metro line, a Monte Carlo simulation considering daily fluctuations in package volume, van capacity, and delivery distances estimates that using metro infrastructure for last mile delivery could avoid, on average, over 16 delivery vans per day, reduce surface traffic by more than 1,600 kilometers, and cut CO₂ emissions by approximately 291 kilograms daily. These figures reinforce the environmental and operational advantages of this innovative logistics approach.

These reductions, extrapolated to Madrid's extensive metro network with 12 lines, would cover approximately 5% of last-mile freight deliveries (currently, around 350,000 parcels are delivered daily in the city of Madrid). However, significant synergies could be achieved if, alongside the model proposed in the FOR-FREIGHT project, other use cases were implemented, such as home delivery using microhubs located in stations. Overall, the impact of using the metro network could result in up to a 15% reduction in delivery vans, CO₂ emissions, and kilometers traveled on surface roads.

Simulation Assumptions

- Number of daily packages: mean = 1,500, standard deviation = 200
- Van capacity (packages per van): mean = 100, standard deviation = 25
- Kilometers traveled per van: mean = 100 km, standard deviation = 15
- CO₂ emissions per kilometer: 0.18 kg/km
- Desired margin of error: 1%
- Number of iterations: 31,060

Simulation Results

Based on the simulation, the following average values were obtained:

- Delivery vans avoided: 16.18
- Surface kilometers avoided: 1,618.59 km
- CO₂ emissions avoided: 291.35 kg

The results of this simulation are perfectly aligned with the key KPIs defined for this scenario in the FOR-FREIGHT project and they serve to quantify the expected benefits, especially the following KPI:

ES1/2_3 Number of vehicles required for last mile delivery with average loading. This reduction would range from 0.5% using a single line and only the locker model to 15% if all metro lines are used and more logistics models are exploited.

ES1/2_4 GHG emissions. The potential reduction in emissions follows a similar pattern to that of delivery vans, but by reducing surface congestion, emissions generated by other vehicles will also be reduced, potentially reaching a 20% reduction in emissions generated by last-mile delivery activity if all metro lines are used and several logistics models are included.

4. CONCLUSIONS

As analyzed by Metro de Madrid, the use of the metro network for last-mile parcel delivery using lockers in stations is a highly ambitious project, but one that has generated enormous interest from logistics and e-commerce companies. The potential benefits and major challenges are outlined in this document, which aims to serve as a basis for any metro network wishing to explore this initiative.

To this end, utilizing the solvers generated in the FOR-FREIGHT project offers an advantage for logistics planning decision-making, as well as a way to standardize information when multiple stakeholders are involved.

Regarding the proposed locker model, the natural evolution would be to leverage the synergies that arise from adding more activities, such as home delivery using microhubs in stations or the transfer of goods to pick-up points or even physical stores or large retail outlets in the city center. The more these synergies are exploited, the greater the economic, social, and environmental benefits will be.

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